

PREDICTING THE CONSTITUTIVE BEHAVIOR OF BIAXIAL BRAIDED COMPOSITES USING BEAM UNIT CELLS

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1. Abstract

Braided composites have a complex internal geometry with two or more sets of intertwined and undulated yarns. The internal geometry strongly depends on the shape of the desired component and on process parameters. This increases the demand for material characterization and constitutive modeling for structural analysis.

This paper presents an approach for the prediction of the nonlinear material behavior of biaxial braided composites using finite element (FE) unit cells. A repeating unit cell (RUC) with beam elements representing the yarns is used for the prediction of the constitutive behavior. The approach, based on Cox's binary model [1], yields several advantages: a fast and automated model generation and meshing process in combination with numerical efficiency due to the decreased number of degrees of freedom (DOFs). Main goal of the unit cell calculations is to predict the influence of the internal geometry of the braided composite onto the elastic, nonlinear and failure behavior. Two biaxial braided composites with 45° and 60° braiding angle are modeled in this paper. Elastic and nonlinear predictions match the experimental results and the stress field obtained correlates well with a classical continuum unit cell.

2. Introduction

The increased demand for carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) accelerates the trend from manual and expensive hand layup towards automated and robust manufacturing processes. Braiding is an automated preforming process for liquid composite molding (LCM): the fibers are formed to a dry fiber preform, which is subsequently impregnated with a polymer resin using a LCM process. The possibility to automate these processes helps to drastically

reduce cycle times and manufacturing costs for high volume production.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1: Braiding machine with 176 bobbins (a); principle of bobbin movement (b)

The braiding process is able to produce near-net-shaped preforms by overbraiding shaped mandrels (Fig. 1): the yarns, stored on bobbins, counter-rotate around the braiding center and create an interlaced yarn pattern that deposits directly on the mandrel. The yarn architecture of a biaxial braid can be compared to a woven fabric, with the difference that the braid offers more variability, e.g. the two yarn directions can be non-orthogonal. The orientation of the yarn directions is defined by the braiding angle θ , which is the angle between the take-up direction of the mandrel and the yarns. A global configuration

of the yarn architecture (e.g. braiding angle, preform thickness, etc.) can be adjusted for mandrels with constant cross-section using the braiding machine process parameters. If either shape or dimension of the mandrel cross-section changes, the yarn architecture varies locally, which leads to changing material properties on the structure.

For the structural analysis of a braided component, these local variations of material properties are a big challenge: a material modeling approach for braided composites has to be able to predict the influence of the internal geometry to the stiffness and strength of the material. This paper uses a multi-scale modeling approach to achieve this. First, on the *micro* scale, micromechanical equations are used to calculate the mechanical properties of impregnated yarns based on fiber and matrix values. These properties are used as an input to the *meso* scale: in unit cell calculations, the yarn architecture of braided composites is used in conjunction with the mechanical properties of yarns and matrix to calculate the yarn architecture influence to the effective properties. The predicted properties can further be used to feed a *macro* scale analysis of a structural component, where mechanical properties of braids with different yarn architectures are needed. This paper mainly focuses on the *meso*-scale simulations, where a novel unit cell comprising beam and continuum elements is used to model the constitutive behavior of braided composites with different yarn architectures.

3. Unit Cell Modeling

3.1. Binary Beam Model (BBM)

The unit cell modeling approach in this paper is based on the idea of Cox's binary model [1]: the longitudinal yarn properties are represented by 1D line elements while the yarn transversal and shear properties as well as the properties of the matrix pockets are represented by the so-called *effective*

medium continuum elements. Thus, the cross-section of the yarn is not discretely modeled as e.g. in a continuum unit cell (Fig. 2), but included through the cross-section definition of the line element. This geometrical idealization offers several advantages: it helps reducing the hand-effort for the unit cell creation and meshing, decreases the model size in terms of degrees of freedom and thus allows for numerically efficient unit cell models.

In contrast to the models published by Cox, which use truss elements for the yarns, the presented approach uses beam elements. This is mainly due to two reasons: beam elements are able to model the bending stiffness of the impregnated yarns and the shape of the cross-section can be considered using the second moments of inertia of the beam. Furthermore beam elements provide information about the bending-induced stresses in the undulation interval. This enables to perform a more detailed stress analysis, which is inevitable when the unit cell is used for a failure analysis.

The unit cell calculations presented were performed using the implicit commercial finite element code Abaqus/Standard 6.11 [4].

3.2. Geometric modeling

Based on the parameters measured from photomicrographs, a geometrical model of the braided composite can be built. The authors use the WiseTex [3] software for this purpose. WiseTex approximates the yarns piecewise using parametrical functions and calculates the yarn path inside the unit cell by minimization of the bending energy. Based on yarn width, yarn height, yarn spacing and braiding angle WiseTex is able to provide a description of the yarn path inside the unit cell. With the command line interface and XML data format of WiseTex [5], the geometrical modeling can be integrated straightforward into the unit cell analysis by using e.g. Python scripting. For the binary beam

Fig. 2: Binary beam model: yarns in the unit cell are idealized using beam elements and embedded into the continuum elements of the effective medium

model, the coordinates of the yarn path are exported from the Wise Tex XML file for further usage in the FE model.

3.3. Elastic material model

A parametric model should be able to model braided composites with different fiber volume fractions, which means that the packing density κ (fiber volume fraction in the yarn) and thus the material properties of the yarn may change. The elastic constants used for the binary beam model are therefore calculated using a micromechanical approach. Chamis' micro-mechanical model was chosen for this task as it is commonly used for the calculation of yarn properties [6].

Main idealization of the binary beam model is to split up the yarn properties into longitudinal and transversal properties, which are modeled by different types of elements. This requires a modified definition of the material properties: the beam elements representing the axial and bending stiffness of the yarns are assigned the yarn stiffness, which means that the packing density κ is used as fiber volume fraction. Furthermore it should be considered that beam elements (BE) and effective medium (EM) continuum elements fill out the same space superimposing the material properties of both. To prevent double accounting of transversal stiffness of the yarns, the transversal yarn modulus has to be subtracted from the longitudinal yarn stiffness. The effective medium shall represent transversal and shear properties of the yarns as well as properties of the matrix pockets. Consequently, the overall fiber volume fraction of the unit cell is used for the calculation of these properties. An overview of the material property assignment is given in eq. (1)-(3).

$$E^{BE} = E_{11}^{YARN}(\varphi_f = \kappa) - \quad (1)$$

$$E_{22}^{YARN}(\varphi_f = \kappa)$$

$$E^{EM} = E_{22}(\varphi_f = \varphi_f^{RUC}) \quad (2)$$

$$G^{EM} = G_{12}(\varphi_f = \varphi_f^{RUC}) \quad (3)$$

In this publication, beam and effective medium elastic constants are calculated based on coupon test data: unidirectional (UD) and bulk matrix tests results are used to calculate fiber properties, which

are then used for prediction of elastic yarn properties at the desired fiber volume fraction.

3.4. Plasticity model

The constitutive behavior of most carbon fiber reinforced plastics in matrix dominated loadings exhibits strong nonlinearities before final failure. These nonlinearities are due to different mechanisms occurring at the microscopic level and the nature of these effects can be different: e.g. transversal inter-yarn cracking, viscoelastic or plastic deformation inside the matrix can be the source. Description and modeling of these effects with a physical based model goes beyond the scope of the current study. But as the mechanical response of biaxial braided composites, e.g. for the take-up direction of a ($\pm 45^\circ$) braid, may be governed by the matrix properties, a possibility to account for these nonlinearities is included in the binary beam model.

As shown by Flores et. al. [7] a convenient and efficient implementation of the matrix nonlinearities may be achieved by using an elastic-plastic material model in the isotropic effective medium.

Fig. 3: Linear Drucker-Prager yield criterion with fully associated flow and isotropic hardening in the p-t plane

Analogous to [7] a Drucker-Prager yield criterion (Fig. 3) with a fully associated flow rule and an isotropic hardening function was chosen for the effective medium. A general form of the yield criterion is given by

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) = \sigma_e - \tan(\beta) * p - \sigma_0, \quad (4)$$

where σ_e is the von-Mises stress and p the hydrostatic pressure. The term $\tan(\beta)$ describes the pressure dependence of the yield criterion and σ_0 is the yield stress whose dependence to the accumulated plastic strain is given by the hardening

Fig. 4: Multi-point constraints for coupling of beam and continuum element nodes (a) and mesh of unit cell with beam elements (blue) constraint by MPCs (b)

law. For the calibration of the yield function, the parameter β has to be obtained and an appropriate hardening function has to be given. The nonlinear behavior of biaxial braided composites is believed to be mainly due to the shear-nonlinearity of the transversely isotropic yarns. Therefore, a shear hardening curve from a ($\pm 45^\circ$) experiment using unidirectional plies of the same fiber/matrix combination is used for the calibration. Additionally the pressure dependency was taken from [8].

3.5. Coupling of beam and continuum elements

The binary beam model uses two different types of elements namely beam and continuum elements to represent yarns and matrix in the unit cell. Beam and continuum elements are superimposed in the geometric definition of the unit cell, but the degrees of freedom of the elements are not inherently coupled. A method employing multi-point constraints (MPCs) is used in this paper to couple the translational displacements of the two. Every beam element node is allocated to a continuum host element and the translation DOFs of the beam node are constraint to be equal to the interpolated nodal displacements of the hosting continuum element. The interpolation is performed by means of the beam nodes' relative position in the continuum element. This approach, in contrast to node sharing, allows the meshes of beam and continuum elements to be independent in size and ensures a hexahedral continuum element mesh (Fig. 4). The coupling of beam and continuum elements can be easily introduced into the analysis by using the *embedded elements* function available in Abaqus.

3.6. Gauge averaging

For the prediction of failure inside a structure, commonly local stress fields (point stresses) are used. For the binary beam model, the stresses associated with matrix-dominated failure modes are taken from the effective medium. Due to the coupling of beam and continuum elements, singularities in the stress field of the effective medium arise, i.e. that these stresses are mesh-dependent and shall not be used for failure analysis. To overcome this problem an averaging scheme based on the idea of gauge averaging [9] is used in this paper. Gauge averaging bases on the idea that the failure modes of a composite are connected to distinct length scales, thus a stress averaged over certain length or volume should be used for the failure prediction.

Fig. 5: Beam element node (cross) and corresponding nodes for volume averaging

In this paper, volume averaged stresses are calculated: for every beam node an averaging volume is defined and the nodes of the effective medium lying inside the averaging volume are associated to this node. In the post-processing the

stress tensor of the beam node is calculated by averaging the stress tensors of the continuum nodes (Fig. 5). It can be shown that the stresses obtained by this averaging procedure are mesh-independent and can be used for a failure analysis.

3.7. Periodic boundary conditions

A rhombic representative unit cell is used in all calculations, where the angle of the rhombus changes with the braiding angle. The shape of the unit cell including the periodicity vectors is given in Fig. 6. Two-dimensional periodic boundary conditions in the form of eq. (5) are used for all calculations. The periodic boundary conditions couple the translational degrees of freedom of the effective medium nodes on adjacent faces, which implicitly includes the beam nodes lying on the faces, as these are coupled using the MPCs described above.

$$u^{Face1} - u^{Face2} = \Delta u^{1-2} \quad (5)$$

The macroscopic loading of the unit cell is introduced via so-called masternodes, controlling the relative displacement between two adjacent faces. The loading can be force or displacement controlled, where the effective stresses respectively strains are calculated from the masternode forces and displacements according to [10].

Fig. 6: Shape of rhombic repeating unit cell and periodicity vectors

Additionally to the in-plane boundary conditions, an appropriate out-of-plane support has to be defined. In this paper, the lower side of the unit cell was fixed, while the upper side was left free to deform. This is equivalent to assuming an out-of-phase (OP)

stacking of a two ply laminate. The OP boundary condition was chosen, as there is not a unique definition valid for a laminate consisting of different stacking as observed for the braids investigated in this study (Fig. 7). Furthermore, for such mixed stacking laminates, the out-of-plane deformation is believed to be rather small and closer to the OP-stacking case.

Fig. 7: Stacking of plies in a ($\pm 45^\circ$) braided laminate

3.8. Implementation

The procedure of creation, meshing and analysis of the binary beam model was integrated into a MATLAB routine including all pre- and post-processing steps: the WiseTex model is build using the XML data format and command line interface. The yarn paths are transferred into the Abaqus/CAE preprocessor, where the model is created, meshed and material properties are defined. Following up, the periodic boundary conditions are added to the model and the analysis is started. After the analysis the necessary post-processing steps are conducted.

4. Study Case / Material description

In this study the constitutive behavior of a 2x2 biaxial braided composite consisting of *Toho Tenax HTS 40 12K t0* carbon fiber yarns and *HexFlow® RTM6* epoxy resin is modeled. The braid preforms were produced using a *Herzog* braiding machine consisting of 176 bobbins (Fig. 1). Braids of different braiding angles, namely 45° and 60° were considered. The experimental results used for assessment of the model predictions were obtained by coupon tests: the yarns were braided on a cylindrical mandrel, cut and draped down on a flat surface. Eight plies were stacked on top of each other and impregnated using the vacuum assisted

process (VAP). Coupons were cut out of the panels and tested according to the AITM 1-0007 [11] standard.

As the discrete architecture of the fibers is modeled in the unit cell, geometric parameters of the braided composites are needed as an input for the model. Photomicrographs were cut out at several positions of the cured braid laminates. A microscope was used to measure yarn width, yarn height, yarn spacing and laminate thickness. Tab. 1 gives an overview of the geometric parameters used for modeling.

The material properties of impregnated yarns and matrix pockets inside the braided composites were obtained by coupon testing. Unidirectional laminates using the same fiber and matrix combination were produced by filament winding and impregnated using VAP. Coupons were cut out of the test panels and tension and compression tests were conducted in longitudinal and transversal direction.

5. Elastic results

Biaxial braided composites with different braiding angles, namely 45° and 60° were investigated. The geometric parameters given in Tab. 1 were used to build up unit cell models and linear elastic FE calculations were performed. Three load cases, tension in 11-direction, tension in 22-direction and in-plane shear (Fig. 6) are needed to obtain the elastic constants. The average stress and strain in the unit cell is calculated from displacements and forces at the masternodes. The three load cases provide all entries of the in-plane stress stiffness matrix, thus the stiffness in any other direction may be calculated.

Tab. 2 shows a comparison of the elastic constants obtained from the binary beam model to method of inclusions (TexComp [3]) as well as experimental results. It can be seen that the model correlates very well with the experimental results. The binary beam model slightly overestimates the stiffness in all cases, which mainly is attributed to two reasons: the experimental modulus is obtained in the strain

interval from 0.1 % to 0.3 %. In this strain interval the material behavior of the matrix dominated load cases (11 and 22) is already nonlinear, which leads to a lower modulus compared to the initial one obtained by the linear elastic calculations. In addition the fixed out-of-plane displacement of the unit cell presents the stiffer limit, which is mainly seen for the fiber dominated (1F) load cases. The bigger deviation of 12.1% in the 22-direction in the ($\pm 60^\circ$) braided composites is attributed to deviations of the braiding angle inside the test panel, which have a major impact onto the stiffness. Overall the elastic predictions obtained by the binary beam model correlate very well with the experimental results.

6. Influence of nonlinearities

Several types of nonlinear effects in textile composites are reported in literature. For a classification the sources of nonlinearity can be divided into two groups: geometrical and material nonlinearities. Geometrical nonlinearities are due to the discrete reinforcement of the fibers, which has a defined structure that deforms under loading. The most interesting effects for biaxial braided composites are the rotation of the fibers towards the load (scissoring) and the straightening of undulated fibers (Fig. 8). Material nonlinearities are mostly induced by the matrix as described in section 3.4.

6.1. Geometric nonlinearities

Geometric nonlinearities are considered in the unit cell by including big deformations into the FE analysis. The results of a geometric nonlinear unit cell analysis are exemplarily shown for a ($\pm 45^\circ$) braid in Fig. 9: For tension in the fiber direction (1F), no influence of fiber stretching can be seen, whereas the tension in take-up direction (11) shows some deviations from the linear solution. But it should be noted that in the strain range where the materials investigated in this study fail, the discrepancy is less than 3% between linear and

Tab. 1: Geometric parameters measured from photomicrographs

braiding angle [°]	yarn width [mm]	yarn height [mm]	spacing [mm]	laminate height [mm]	packing density [%]
45	3.10	0.28	3.05	3.89	67
60	2.42	0.37	2.17	3.05	66

Tab. 2: Comparison of elastic predictions from the binary beam model to experimental results

Direction	braiding angle	Youngs Modulus [GPa]		Experiment	Deviation [%]
		Predictions			
		TexComp	Binary Beam Model		
11	45°	13880	14607	13100 ± 500	11.5%
1F	45°	71040	72220	68200 ± 2100	5.9%
11	60°	8134	9033	8476 ± 643	6.6%
22	60°	39660	41673	37172 ± 2444	12.1%

nonlinear solution. For the other study cases, the obtained results were similar, so it can be summed up that nonlinear geometric effects may be more dominant for materials with higher failure strains, but have only minor influence to the mechanical response of the braided composites in this study.

Fig. 8: Nonlinear geometrical effect (a) yarn straightening (b) yarn scissoring

6.2. Material nonlinearities

The presented paper uses a phenomenological material model to describe the nonlinear material behavior before final failure observed in braided composites. Both, matrix microcracking and plastic deformation is modeled using an elasto-plastic material model with a linear Drucker-Prager yield criterion for the effective medium. This is sufficient for the current case, as only monotonically increasing loads are investigated. The plasticity model was calibrated as described in section 3.4 and assigned to the effective medium.

The results obtained from the non-linear material model are exemplarily shown for a ($\pm 45^\circ$) braided composite in Fig. 10: For the fiber direction (*1F*) the model predicts a linear stress-strain behavior, which is in good correlation with the experimental results. It should be noted that the oscillations in the test curve are non-physical and due to the blistering of the stochastic dot pattern applied on the specimen surface for the digital image correlation (DIC) strain

measurements. For the take-up direction (*11*), the material behavior is rather non-linear which can be predicted by the plasticity model in the effective medium. It should be noted that, as for the *1F*-direction, the strain measurement failed before final failure, i.e. the end of the stress-strain curve is not the final failure.

7. Stress analysis:

As described in section 3.6 the stress analysis of the binary beam model is conducted by applying volume averaging to the stress field inside the effective medium. In the presented calculations a cylindrical averaging volume with a diameter of half the yarn width and a height equal to the yarn height is used. To account for the periodicity of the stress field, all averaging volumes intersecting the faces of the unit cell include the corresponding nodes on adjacent face of the unit cell. The validity of the gauge averaging approach is checked in this paper by comparing the volume-averaged stresses to the ones obtained by a full continuum model. For this purpose, two models of a ($\pm 45^\circ$) biaxial braided composite were built based on the same geometric model.

The models were analyzed in a linear elastic finite element calculation with a uniaxial load applied in one of the yarn directions. As the gauge averaging calculates the yarn stresses for every beam element node, the comparison of the models is given in terms of yarn normal stresses. Fig. 11 (a) shows the longitudinal stress on the bottom of a yarn in the loading direction: the binary beam model is able to reproduce the bending-induced stress concentrations in the crimp interval of the yarn. Both, the position of the stress peaks as well as the magnitude are captured by the BBM.

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Fig. 9: stress strain curve from a geometrical nonlinear analysis

Fig. 10: Comparison of non-linear simulations to experiments

The transversal stress in a yarn perpendicular to the loading direction is shown in Fig. 11 (b). The graph shows that the local variations of the stress along the yarn predicted by the continuum model are also captured by the BBM. The stress along the beam element is smoother than the one from the continuum model, which is due to the averaging procedure, but the general trend and the magnitude of the stress are captured well.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11: Stresses obtained from the binary beam model compared to a full continuum model

8. Conclusion

Based on Cox's binary model a finite element unit cell comprising of beam and continuum elements was developed for the analysis of biaxial braided composites. Material models for linear-elastic and elastic-plastic material behavior of yarns and matrix are given. Furthermore an averaging procedure is introduced that allows a mesh-independent solution of the stress field inside the effective medium. Elastic predictions are compared to experimental values and a good accordance is obtained. The nonlinear simulations showed that the effects of nonlinear material behavior dominate the response of the unit cells and that the elastic-plastic material introduced is able to capture this. Finally a comparison of the gauge-averaged stress field inside a yarn to a full continuum model showed that the gauge-averaged stresses are in good correlation to the ones obtained by the classical continuum solution. Further studies will be conducted concerning the prediction of failure using the binary beam model.

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